

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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- President of the 13th STC Congress

Petar Bulat

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SVEST I STAVOVI BUDUĆIH ZDRAVSTVENIH RADNIKA U SRBIJI O NOVIM PSIHOAKTIVNIM SUPSTANCAMA

CLINICAL
TOXICOLOGY

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Znanje zdravstvenih radnika (ZR) o novim psihoaktivnim supstancama (NPAS) predstavlja kamen temeljac za inicijative kliničkih toksikologa u suočavanju sa ovim novim svetskim fenomenom. Rezultati nedavno objavljenih studija ukazuju na neadekvatno osnovno znanje i veštine ZR neophodnih za uspešno lečenje pacijenata koji koriste NPAS. Istraživanje je sprovedeno kako bi se procenila svest (znanje) i stavovi budućih ZR o NPAS u kontekstu njihove nadolazeće uloge u prevenciji i lečenju predoziranja i zavisnosti od NPAS. Takođe, analizirani su i svi parametri koji stupaju u korelaciju sa percepcijom i korišćenjem NPAS kod budućih ZR. U studiji preseka, koja je sprovedena 2017. godine, učestvovalo je 490 studenata medicine, farmacije i stomatologije Medicinskog fakulteta Univerziteta u Novom Sadu. Svest o NPAS je bila bolja kod studenata farmacije (IRR: 1,926, CI: 1,173-3,163, p=0,010) nego kod studenata medicine – studenti farmacije su prepoznali čak 92,6% više NPAS imena od svojih vršnjaka koji studiraju medicinu.

Studentkinje su znale 36,5% manje NPAS imena od svojih muških kolega (IRR: 0,635, CI: 0,399-1,013, p=0,049). Broj NPAS imena koje su učesnici studije znali rastao je za 15,9% sa svakom godinom uzrasta – što je starost studenata bila veća, znali su više o NPAS (IRR: 1,159, CI: 1.025-1,310, p=0,018). Studenti koji su koristili marihuana znali su 52,6% više NPAS imena od onih koji nikada nisu imali iskustva sa kanabisom (IRR: 1,526, CI: 0,953-2,445, p=0,049). Iako je veliki broj budućih ZR tvrdio da zna šta su NPAS, uočene su brojne zablude. Neophodni su dalji obrazovni naponi kako bi se poboljšalo njihovo znanje i stavovi u vezi sa NPAS.

KLJUČNE REČI: nove psihoaktivne supstance, svest, stavovi, studenti, zdravstveni radnici

AWARENESS AND ATTITUDES OF FUTURE HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONALS IN SERBIA TOWARDS NEW PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCES

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Health care provider awareness is recognized as a headstone of clinical toxicology initiatives in taking up the upcoming threat presented by new psychoactive substances (NPS). Recently published studies have underlined the inadequacy in essential knowledge and skills required by health care professionals (HCPs) to successfully treat patients overdosed by NPS. The study was conducted in order to evaluate prospective HCPs awareness and attitudes regarding NPS in the context of their future role in prevention and treatment of NPS overdose and addiction. Correlates of NPS perception and use were also examined.

This cross-sectional survey was performed on 490 students of the Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia, during 2017. NPS awareness was better in pharmacy students (IRR: 1.926, CI: 1.173-3.163, $p=0.010$) than in medicine students – pharmacy students recognized 92.6% more NPS names than their peers studying medicine. Female students knew 36.5% less NPS names than their male colleagues (IRR: 0.635, CI: 0.399-1.013, $p=0.049$). Number of NPS names students know was rising 15.9% with each age year—the higher the age, the larger the number of NPS they were aware of (IRR: 1.159, CI: 1.025-1.310, $p=0.018$). Students who had used marijuana knew 52.6% more NPS names than those who had never had experience with cannabis (IRR: 1.526, CI: 0.953-2.445, $p=0.049$). Although a high number of future HCPs claimed to know what NPS are, numerous misconceptions were noticed. Further educational efforts are necessary to improve their awareness and attitudes regarding NPS.

KEYWORDS: new psychoactive substances, awareness, attitudes, students, health care professionals